

EIC User Group Newsletter

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NEWS

- After US Secretary of Energy **approved the CD-0** (“Approve Mission Need”) and US Dept. of Energy (DOE) [selected Brookhaven National Lab \(BNL\)](#) for building the EIC, the initiative launched by the EICUG Steering Committee (SC) on **EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Studies** (in short, the “Yellow Report document”) has received an important boost. The activities have been organized in **two Working Groups (WG)**, one on **Physics** requirements and one on **Detector** concepts, plus an additional one on future opportunities for accelerator experiments at EIC. Each WG has 4 Conveners and is further organized in **smaller sub-groups**, each one with its own **sub-Conveners**. If you are interested in **joining** a specific group, or simply in being kept informed on the progress, please do the following:
 - * go to the [“Yellow Report” menu of the EICUG web page](#)
 - * follow the highlighted links **“Physics Group”** or **“Detector Group”**
 - * in each corresponding web page, you can find:
 - ❖ the list of names and email addresses of the **Conveners**
 - ❖ the list of **sub-groups** (5 for the “Physics Group” and 11 for the “Detector Group”), each one with its list of names and email addresses of the **co-Conveners** and of the **contact person**
 - ❖ the link to past meetings with uploaded material (Indico)
 - ❖ the **Google calendar** of planned meetings
 - ❖ the **mailing lists**
 - * if you are **interested in a specific sub-group**, send an email to the corresponding contact person

- In the [“Yellow Report” menu of the EICUG web page](#), there is also:
 - * the calendar of **4 workshops** announced by the SC to monitor and discuss the progress of the various working sub-groups. The **dates and locations** are:
 1. [19-21 March 2020, Temple Univ. - Philadelphia \(USA\)](#)
 2. 22-24 May 2020, Univ. and INFN - Pavia - Pavia (Italy)
 3. 17-19 September 2020, CUA - Washington D.C. (USA)
 4. 19-21 November 2020, UCB - Berkeley (USA)
 - * the link to the **Google groups** for a discussion forum of each working sub-group
 - * a [pre-CDR document](#) with information on the present EIC design useful for working sub-group activities
 - * a [draft](#) of the outline of the Yellow Report document

- The last **EICUG remote quarterly meeting** was held on Jan. 23rd 2020, 10-12am EST. The **attendance** was **very high**, reaching the maximum number (100) of permitted simultaneous connections (because of this limit, other users could not log in; the SC is actively searching for a solution to overcome this limitation). Among various items, the following ones were discussed:
 - * **status and organization of Physics WG**: [link to slides](#), presented by the Convener Olga Evdokimov
 - * **status and organization of the Detector WG**: [link to slides](#), presented by the Convener Tanja Horn
 - * **overview of Yellow Report activities** (including a possible outline of the Yellow Report document): [link to slides](#), presented by Thomas Ullrich on behalf also of Rolf Ent and the SC.

NEWS from the SOFTWARE WORKING GROUP

During the last **EICUG remote quarterly meeting** on Jan. 23rd 2020, the co-Convener Markus Diefenthaler presented the [status and organization of the EICUG Software Working Group](#). A series of **EIC Software Tutorials** on JupyterLab environment and on Detector full simulations have been held on 2020, Jan. 9 and 29, and recently on Feb. 6 (here, the [Indico page](#)). For more detailed information, see the [EIC Software web page](#).

NEWS from the INSTITUTIONAL BOARD

- The EIC User Group (**EICUG**) is **growing!** We welcome the following new institutions:
 - University of Wuppertal (Germany)
 - University of California, Davis (US)
 - Christopher Newport University (US)
 - Indian Institute of Technology Indore (India)
 - Kobe University (Japan)
 - Florida State University (US)
 - Université Catholique de Louvain (Belgium)
 - University of Rzeszow (Poland)
- The EICUG currently stands at 1033 members, from 211 institutions in 31 countries. Theory members are approximately 25%, experimentalists 60%, experts in accelerators 14%, the remaining being administrative support.

NEWS from ELECTION and NOMINATION COMMITTEE

- The **term of Ernst Sichtermann** as “At-large Member” of the EICUG Steering Committee **ended** on Oct. 31 2019, and it has been extended to Dec. 31st in order to coordinate elections in January and/or July of each year, as needed. The elections were open on Dec. 5th 2019 and they have been completed. The elected **new at-large member of the SC is Barbara Jacak** (Lawrence Berkeley National Lab and University of California, Berkeley), whose term will end in Dec. 31st, 2021.

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- During the last **EICUG remote quarterly meeting** on Jan. 23rd 2020, Ralf Seidl (Chair) presented the [status of the Conference & Talks Committee](#). For further details about **upcoming conferences** and workshops see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> . For a list of **open EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/open> . For a list of **previous EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (often including also a link to the presentation). If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or if in general you wish to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, please contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (includes also links to some presentations)

[13th European Research Conference on Electromagnetic Interactions with Nucleons and Nuclei](#), Paphos (Cyprus), 27 October - 2 November 2019

[CHEP 2019](#), Adelaide (Australia), 3-8 November 2019

[Quark Matter 2019](#), Wuhan (China), 4-8 November 2019

[EIC Streaming Readout workshop](#), BNL Upton (NY - USA), 13-15 November 2019

[LPC Workshop on Physics Connections the LHC and EIC](#), FermiLab (IL - USA), 13-15 November 2019

[Forward Physics and QCD at LHC](#), Guanajuato (Mexico), 18-23 November 2019

[MCEGs for future ep and eA facilities](#), Vienna (Austria), 20-22 November 2019

[Resummation, Evolution, Factorization \(REF 2019\)](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 November 2019

[CPAD Instrumentation Frontier Workshop](#), Madison (WI - USA), 8-10 December 2019

[EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Developments kick-off meeting](#), MIT - Boston (MA - USA), 12-13 December 2019

[International workshop on QCD with EIC \(QEIC\)](#), Bombay (India), 4-7 January 2020

[Exploring QCD with light nuclei at EIC](#), Stony Brook (NY - US), 21-24 January 2020

[EIC Detector R&D Committee Meeting](#), Upton (NY - US), 30-31 January 2020

[Correlations in Partonic and Hadronic Interactions \(CPHI-2020\)](#), CERN-Geneva (Switzerland), 3-7 February 2020

[2020 Santa Fe Jets and Heavy Flavor Workshop](#), Santa Fe (NM - US), 3-5 February 2020

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> and <http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html>

[Winter Workshop on Nuclear Dynamics](#), Puerto Vallarta (Mexico), 1-7 March 2020

[A.I. for Nuclear Physics Workshop](#), Jefferson Lab - Newport News (VA-US), 3-6 March 2020

[KEK Workshop on Femtotechnologies by quantum computers 2020](#), Tsukuba (Japan), 7 March 2020

[1st EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Workshop](#), Philadelphia (MD-US), 19-21 March 2020

[DIS 2020](#), Brooklyn (NY - USA), 23-27 March 2020

[Rencontres de Moriond, QCD and high-energy interactions](#), La Thuile (Italy), 28 March - 4 April 2020

[Jet observables at an Electron Ion Collider](#), Upton (NY - US), 15-17 April 2020

[QCD Evolution 2020](#), Los Angeles (CA - US), 27 April - 1 May 2020

[Origin of the Visible Universe: Unraveling the Proton Mass \(INT-20-77W\)](#), INT Seattle (WA - US), 4 - 8 May 2020

[The 17th International Workshop on Hadron Structure and Spectroscopy](#), Trieste (Italy), 17-22 May 2020

[2nd EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Workshop](#), Pavia (Italy), 22-24 May 2020

[Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020

[Joint GlueX-PANDA-EIC Workshop on Machine Learning for Particle Physics Experiments](#), Darmstadt (Germany), 25-29 May 2020

[Hard Probes](#), Austin (TX - USA), 1-6 June 2020

[Tomography of light nuclei at an EIC](#), ECT*-Trento (Italy), 15-19 June 2020

[LXX International Conference NUCLEUS-2020](#), Saint Petersburg (Russia), 26-30 June 2020

[Light-Cone 2020](#), Jeju (Korea), 29 June - 4 July 2020

[40th International Conference on High Energy Physics \(ICHEP 2020\)](#), Prague (Czech Republic), 30 July - 5 August 2020

EIC Users Group Meeting 2020, Miami (F - USA), 3-7 August 2020

[Photonuclear Gordon Conference](#), Holderness (NH - USA), 9-14 August 2020

[22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#), Lisbon (Portugal), 31 August - 4 September 2020

[24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 20-25 September 2020

[Baryon 2020](#), Sevilla (Spain), 22-25 September 2020

[New Physics Phenomena - Hadronic Contributions to New Physics Searches](#), Crete (Greece), 24-30 September 2020

[Lepton-Photon 2021](#), Manchester (UK), 9-14 August 2021

Quarks and Nucleon Physics QNP 2021, Bonn (Germany), 20-24 September 2021